

$p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ for Identical Photons the Basic Idea Behind the Bose-Einstein Distribution Part 3

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 14, 2025

In Parts 1 and 2, we argued that an unnormalized distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is applied to the distribution of E over identical particles not only in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, but also in the case of photons, for which only photons with the same frequency may be considered identical. In such a case, unlike the MB one, one does not know N , the number of identical frequency vs photons. One does not even know E_s , the energy of these identical photons, only E_{total} which represents photons of all vs values, e.g. vs_1, vs_2, vs_3 . The point we made in Parts 1 and 2, is that one uses the unnormalized $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in both the classical MB case and the quantum photon case. (Furthermore it is used in the general Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac cases⁰. In the photon case, one considers $E_s = \sum_r r \exp(-vs_r)$, where r is the number of vs photons in a cell. The number of N_s cells is given by Volume * volume of spherical shell of radius proportional vs ($\hbar=1, c=1$).

Here, we note the existence in nature of distributions other than the Maxwell-Boltzmann one and ask: Why does quantum mechanics only use the MB $\exp(-e_i/T)$ unnormalized distribution? It is not only the photon case, but the general Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac cases (with a chemical potential and the grand canonical partition function) which also utilize $\exp(-e_i/T)$ at the root. Furthermore, in a bound state one has $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and if one writes $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, then $\exp(ipx)\exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$ which follows the MB pattern except that it applies to momentum. We ask: Why could one not use another distribution, for example the Kaniadakis one for which $\exp_k(x)\exp_k(-x)=1$ where $x=-e_i/T$? We try to write the Bose-Einstein distribution in this Kaniadakis case. We note that this is purely speculative and are not aware if there are any experimental deviations from the usual Bose-Einstein distribution for bosons. Nevertheless, we think it is useful to have an expression in case there exist some experimental deviations which it might fit in this approach.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Underlying the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac Cases

The Maxwell-Boltzmann-Shannon unnormalized distribution factor $\exp(-e_i/T)$ (or $\exp(-E/T)$ when applied to a system) also appears in the quantum Bose-Einstein (BE) and Fermi-Dirac (FD) cases. In fact, in the high energy limit and low density both of these become MB distributions (.1). It has been argued in the literature that even the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution follows from a quantum mechanical treatment and this is consistent with it appearing as a limiting case of the BE and FD distributions.

As a result, we wish to try to examine the physical idea behind $\exp(-e_i/T)$. We have suggested in Parts 1 and 2 that it applies to a special distribution of energy E over a certain number of identical particles. In other words, it is consistent with a physics of interactions in which energy is like a transactional quantity which has no particular restrictions other than it be conserved. Thus, $p(e_i)$ really carries the information e_i/T and not much else. There are no special restrictions about an interaction which depend on energy of the constituents, but a priori one

need not expect this to be the case. For example, there could be various e_i thresholds in an interaction. For example, if a particle has energy e_1 then it interacts in one way whereas if it has e_2 , it interacts in a somewhat different manner. There could be e_i dependent interaction rules with finite threshold limits. This, we argue, would break the notion of

$$p(e_i)p(e_j)p(e_k) = p(e_l)p(e_m) \text{ if } e_i+e_j+e_k=e_l+e_m \quad ((1))$$

The probability may not simply be a carrier of the information e_i/T , there may be specific e_i thresholds or special considerations involved. $\exp(-e_i/T)$ may not be the correct factor to consider in all cases, even though it has had presumably remarkable experimental success since about the 1860s (2). In fact, it was not until about 1988 that the Tsallis distribution appeared and about 2001, the Kaniadakis. Nevertheless, these two and many others seem to match certain experimental situations. This begs the question: Why do the quantum Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac distributions ultimately follow $\exp(-e_i/T)$ at their root?

It is well-known that the BE and FD distributions become the MB in the e_i/T or $(e_i-u)/T$ (u =chemical potential) limit, but they are both based on the factor $\exp(-1/T(E-uN))$ with $N=0,1,2,3,4\dots$ etc for bosons and $N=0,1$ for fermions. Thus, the MB $\exp(-E/T)$ is present in the quantum case. We argued in Parts 1 and 2 that it is linked to a distribution of energy over identical particles. In the MB case, all N particles are identical, but in the BE and FD cases, only particles with the same kinetic energy/momentum are identical because of the physical frequency \hbar/E and wavelength \hbar/p .

As a result, no energy dependent specifics are assigned to an interaction, one only imposes the idea that particles with the same e_i are identical and so the MB $\exp(-e_i/T)$ applies to them. This leads to the geometric series of the Bose-Einstein case (see Part 2) or the $1+\exp(-e_i/T)$ factor of the FD case.

The Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution Applied to Quantum Momentum

The BE and FD cases are not the only examples of the $\exp(-e_i/T)$ type factor appearing in quantum mechanics. We argue that the free particle wavefunction (spatial part) $\exp(ipx)$ (and even the temporal one as well) follow this pattern, i.e.

$$\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T) \text{ and } \exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((2))$$

If one writes: $V(x) = \text{potential} = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ for a bound quantum single particle problem then:

$$VW \text{ (} W=\text{wavefunction)} \text{ leads to } \exp(ikx)\exp(ipx) = \exp(i(p+k)x) \text{ terms which are like } p+k \text{ terms.} \quad ((3))$$

The idea of the distribution of a quantity e_i or p over identical particles with the probability essentially carrying the e_i/T or p information appears strongly in quantum mechanics. One may ask, however: Why does not one see distribution other than $\exp(-e_i/T)$ or $\exp(ipx)$?

Speculation of a Bose-Einstein Distribution Based on the Kaniadakis $\exp_k(e_i/T)$

As a simple exercise, we list the BE distribution using a Kaniadakis distribution:

$$\exp_k(x) = \{ kx + \sqrt{1+k^2x^2} \}^{\text{power } 1/k} \text{ where } k=-e_i/T \text{ and } 0 < |k| < 1 \quad ((4))$$

In the $\exp(-e_i/T)$ case:

$$\ln\{Z\} = \text{Sum over } s \ln\{ \text{Sum over } n=0, \text{ infinite } \exp(-(e_s-u)n/T) \}$$

$$n_s = d/dz \ln \{ 1 / (1 - \exp(-(e_s-u)/T)) \} \text{ where } z = \exp(-u/T)$$

$$= 1 / \{ \exp((e_s-u)/T) - 1 \} \quad ((5))$$

This approach is equivalent to an energy one, i.e.

$$E_{\text{total}} = \text{Sum over } s \ e_s \{ [\text{Sum over } n=0, \text{ infinite } n \exp(-(e-u)n/T)] / [\text{Sum over } n=0, \text{ infinite } \exp(-(e-u)n/T)] \} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{i.e. } E_{\text{total}} = \text{Sum over } s \ e_s n_s \quad ((7))$$

It seems that using $\exp_1(x)\exp_k(-x)=1$, one may simply replace $\exp(-(e_s-u)/T)$ with $\exp_k(-(e_i-u)/T)$ to obtain:

$$n_s \text{ (Kaniadakis)} = 1 / \{ \exp_k((e_i-u)/T) - 1 \} \quad ((8))$$

In the $k \gg 0$ or $(e_i-u)/T \ll 1$ limit, $\exp_k(-(e_i-u)/T) \rightarrow \exp(-e_i/T)$. ((9))

In the $(e_i-u)/T \gg 1$ limit, for $k, 0$, one obtains a power law proportional to (e_i/T) power $-1/k$ which matches the Kaniadakis instead of MB case. For $(e_i-u)/T$ neither tiny nor very large, however, one should see differences with the usual Bose-Einstein result. The question is whether such a result appears in nature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor is not just at the root of the MB distribution, but also of the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac distributions which are clearly quantum mechanical. We have argued in Parts 1 and 2 that $\exp(-e_i/T)$ (or the system form $\exp(-E/T)$) suggests a distribution of energy among identical particles in such a way that the probability only conveys the information $-e_i/T$. In other words, there are no special e_i -interaction thresholds or special rules. It is possible, however, that in nature there exist situations in which such special rules hold. In particular, we note that distributions such as the Tsallis and Kaniadakis exist in nature. As a result, we consider calculating the usual Bose-Einstein distribution using (Kaniadakis) $\exp_k(-(e_i-u)/T)$ instead of using $\exp(-e_i/T)$. In such a case, one

has the usual BE case with $\exp(-u/T)$ replaced with $\expk(-u/T)$ because $\expk(x)\expk(-x)=1$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bose%E2%80%93Einstein_statistics
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maxwell%E2%80%93Boltzmann_distribution